

POWER-CONTROL PROBLEMS CAUSED BY FAST FADING IN A DIRECT-SEQUENCE MULTIPLE-ACCESS NETWORK

by

Don Torrieri
Army Research Laboratory

ABSTRACT

When power control is used in a cellular network, the base station attempts to either directly or indirectly track the received power of the desired signal from a mobile. As the fading rate increases, the tracking ability of a direct-sequence code-division multiple-access system deteriorates, and the power-control accuracy declines. It is shown that a large performance degradation occurs when the instantaneous signal level cannot be accurately measured, even when the channel-code interleaving is perfect. An alternative that is assumed by many authors is to measure a long-term-average signal level that averages out the fast fading effects. However, it is shown that this approach is less viable than attempting to track the instantaneous signal level even if the latter results in large errors.

I. INTRODUCTION

The principal difficulty of direct-sequence code-division multiple access (CDMA) is called the *near-far problem*. If all mobiles (users or subscribers) transmit at the same power level, then the received power at a base station is higher for transmitters near the receiving antenna. There is a near-far problem because transmitters that are far from the receiving antenna may be at a substantial power disadvantage, and the spread-spectrum processing gain may not be enough to allow satisfactory reception of their signals. A similar problem may also result from large differences in received power levels due to differences in the shadowing experienced by signals traversing different paths or due to independent fading.

In cellular communication networks, the near-far problem is critical only on the reverse link or uplink because on the forward link or downlink, the base station transmits orthogonal signals synchronously to each mobile associated with it. For cellular networks, the usual solution to the near-far problem is *power control*, whereby all mobiles regulate their power levels. By this means, power control potentially ensures that the power arriving at a common receiving antenna is almost the same for all transmitters. Since solving the near-far problem is essential to the viability of a direct-sequence CDMA network, the accuracy of the power control is a crucial issue.

When closed-loop power control is used, the base station attempts to either directly or indirectly track the received power of the desired signal from a mobile and dynamically transmit a power-control signal [1,2]. The effect of increasing the carrier frequency or the mobile speeds is to increase the fading rate. As the fading rate increases, the tracking ability of a direct-sequence CDMA system deteriorates and the power-control accuracy declines. This problem is often dismissed by invoking the putative tradeoff between the power control and the bit or symbol interleaving [1,2]. It is asserted that the large fade durations during slow fading enable effective power control, whereas the imperfect power control in the presence of fast fading is compensated by the increased effectiveness of the interleaving and channel coding. However, this argument ignores both the potential severity of the near-far problem and the limits of compensation as the fading rate increases. If the power control breaks down completely, then close interfering mobiles can cause frequent error bursts of duration long enough to overwhelm the ability of the deinterleaver to disperse the errors so that the decoder can eliminate them. Thus, some degree of power control must be maintained as the vehicle speeds or the carrier frequency increases. The degree required when the interleaving is perfect is quantified in the next section.

II. IMPACT OF POWER CONTROL ERRORS

Reverse-link capacity is the number of mobiles per cell that can be accommodated over the reverse link at a specified information-bit error rate. Assuming a conventional correlation receiver and typical conditions for cellular communications, the subsequent results indicate that when imperfect power control causes the standard deviation of the received power from each mobile to increase beyond 2 dB, the reverse-link capacity rapidly collapses. The results are consistent with those obtained by several other authors for slow fading (e.g., [1], [3]), but are examined here for fast-fading conditions also.

When the instantaneous signal level cannot be tracked, one might consider measuring the *local-mean power*, which is a long-term-average power that averages out the fast multipath fading component. There is a confusing dichotomy in the literature in that theoretical papers (e.g., [3]–[5]) almost always either tacitly or explicitly assume local-

mean power control despite the fact that proposed power-control systems (e.g., [1], [2]) measure instantaneous power. Accurate local-mean power control eliminates the near-far problem and shadowing effects, but not the effects of the fading. In the subsequent analysis, it is shown that tracking the local-mean power is less useful than attempting to track the instantaneous signal level even if the latter results in large errors.

Consider a direct-sequence CDMA system with *balanced quadrature-phase-shift keying* (QPSK) modulation. This system is used in the reverse link of the IS-95 and third-generation cellular networks. In balanced QPSK, the same binary symbols are carried by the in-phase and quadrature components, and a received direct-sequence desired signal has the form

$$s(t) = \sqrt{S} m(t) p_1(t) \cos \omega_0 t + \sqrt{S} m(t) p_2(t) \sin \omega_0 t \quad (1)$$

where S is the average received power, $m(t)$ represents the data modulation, $p_1(t)$ and $p_2(t)$ are two different spreading waveforms, and ω_0 is the carrier frequency. Coherent demodulation is possible because of the presence of a pilot tone that accompanies each transmitted information-bearing signal. The multiple-access interference in an asynchronous network has the form

$$i(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \left[\sqrt{I_i} q_{1i}(t - \tau_i) \cos(\omega_0 t + \theta_i) + \sqrt{I_i} q_{2i}(t - \tau_i) \sin(\omega_0 t + \theta_i) \right] \quad (2)$$

where I_i is the average power at the receiver of interference signal i , $K-1$ is the number of interfering direct-sequence signals in a cell or sector, $q_{1i}(t)$ and $q_{2i}(t)$ are the products of the data modulation and each of the two spreading sequences of signal i , τ_i is the relative delay of signal i , and θ_i is the phase angle of signal i including the shift due to carrier time delay. The spreading sequences are modeled as independent random binary sequences. The phase angle $\{\theta_i\}$ are assumed to be independent random variables that are uniformly distributed over $[0, 2\pi)$. Let T_s denote the duration of a symbol and T_c the duration of each chip of the spreading waveform. Since only delays modulo- T_c are significant, it is assumed that the time delays $\{\tau_i\}$ are independent and uniformly distributed over $[0, T_c)$. The number of signals per sector K is assumed to be a constant throughout this paper. The receiver for the direct-sequence signal is illustrated in Figure 1, where SWG denotes a spreading waveform generator.

The total energy of the interference per symbol is

$$E_t = \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} E_i \quad (3)$$

where $E_i = I_i T_s$. The received energy of the desired signal per symbol is $E_s = S T_s$. An analysis indicates that the conditional symbol error probability given E_s and E_t is approximately given by [6], [7]

$$P_s(E_s, E_t) = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{N_0 + \sqrt{h} G^{-1} E_t}}\right) \quad (4)$$

where $G = T_s/T_c$ is the processing gain, $N_0/2$ is the two-sided noise power spectral density, and

$$Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2}\right) dy \quad (5)$$

The constant h is determined by the chip waveform; specifically,

$$h = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{3} & , \quad \text{rectangular waveform} \\ \frac{1}{3} + \frac{5}{2\pi^2} & , \quad \text{sinusoidal waveform} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The derivation of (4) requires that

$$E_s \geq \frac{3}{2} \left(N_0 + \frac{E_t}{G} \right) \quad (7)$$

It is assumed that the distributions of E_s and E_t and the values of G and N_0 are such that (7) is satisfied with high probability in the subsequent analysis. We consider three models for power control: perfect instantaneous power control (perfect ipc), imperfect instantaneous power control (imperfect ipc) with lognormally distributed errors, and perfect local-mean power control (perfect lmpc).

If the power control is instantaneous and perfect, then $E_i = E_s = E_{s0}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K-1$. Equation (4) implies that the symbol error probability is

$$P_s = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma_0^{-1} + \sqrt{h} G^{-1} (K-1)}}\right), \quad \text{perfect ipc} \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_0 = E_{s0}/N_0$ is the energy-to-noise-density ratio when the power control is perfect. If the instantaneous power control is imperfect with lognormally distributed errors, then

$$E_s = E_{s0} \varepsilon_0, \quad E_t = E_{s0} \sum_{i=1}^{K-1} \varepsilon_i \quad (9)$$

Figure 1. Receiver for direct-sequence signal with balanced QPSK.

and

$$\varepsilon_i = 10^{\xi_i/10} = \exp(b\xi_i), \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K-1 \quad (10)$$

where $b = (\ln 10)/10$ and each ξ_i is a zero-mean Gaussian random variable with common variance σ_ε^2 . The moments of ε_i , which can be derived from the moment-generating function of ξ_i , are

$$E[\varepsilon_i] = \exp\left(\frac{b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2}{2}\right), \quad E[\varepsilon_i^2] = \exp(2b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2) \quad (11)$$

If K is a constant, then the mean \bar{X} and the variance σ_x^2 of $X = E_t/E_{s0}$ are

$$\bar{X} = (K-1)\exp\left(\frac{b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2}{2}\right), \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_x^2 = (K-1)\left[\exp(2b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2) - \exp(b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2)\right] \quad (13)$$

These equations indicate that if

$$\sqrt{K-1} \gg \exp(b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2/2) \quad (14)$$

then $\bar{X} \gg \sigma_x$, and X is well-approximated by \bar{X} . Since $\varepsilon_0 = \exp(b\xi_0)$, ξ_0 has a Gaussian density, and $X \approx \bar{X}$, the substitution of (9) into (4) and an integration over this density yield

$$P_s = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-x^2/2\sigma_\varepsilon^2)}{\sqrt{2\pi}} g(x) dx, \quad \text{imperfect ipc} \quad (15)$$

where the symbol error probability given that $\xi_0 = x$ is

$$g(x) = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2\exp(bx)}{\gamma_0^{-1} + \sqrt{h}G^{-1}(K-1)\exp(b^2\sigma_\varepsilon^2/2)}}\right) \quad (16)$$

Perfect symbol interleaving is defined as interleaving that causes independent symbol errors in a codeword. Assuming that fast fading enables perfect symbol interleaving, the information-bit error rate for hard-decision decoding of a block code can be calculated from (8) or (15) and [7], [8]

$$P_{ib} \approx \frac{q}{2(q-1)} \left[\sum_{i=t+1}^d \frac{d}{n} \binom{n}{i} P_s^i (1-P_s)^{n-i} + \sum_{i=d+1}^n \binom{n-1}{i-1} P_s^i (1-P_s)^{n-i} \right] \quad (17)$$

where q is the number of symbols in the alphabet, n is the code length, d is the minimum distance, and t is the maximum number of symbol errors that can always be corrected. If r is the code rate and E_b is the energy per bit that is available when the channel symbols are uncoded, then $\gamma_0 = rE_b/N_0$ in (8) and (15).

Suppose that the fading is slow enough that the error in the instantaneous power control is fixed over a codeword duration. Then the information-bit error rate for hard-decision decoding of a block code is

$$P_{ib} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-x^2/2\sigma_\varepsilon^2)}{\sqrt{2\pi}} P_{ib}(g(x)) dx, \quad \text{imperfect ipc} \quad (18)$$

where $P_{ib}(g(x))$ is given by (17) with $g(x)$ substituted for P_s and $g(x)$ is defined by (16).

Assuming the uniform loading of all cells or sectors, there are K mobiles controlled by each base station or sector antenna. The intercell interference from mobiles attached to other base stations or sectors introduces power equal to gKS into a given base station. For a propagation power law equal to 4, independent lognormal shadowing with a standard deviation equal to 8 dB, and perfect power control, it has been found that the intercell interference factor g is approximately equal to 0.63 [4]. The impact of the intercell interference is modeled as equivalent to that of gK additional mobiles in the given cell or sector [5]. Therefore, when intercell interference is taken into account, K is replaced by $K(1 + g)$ in the preceding equations.

Plots of the information-bit error rate versus $K(1 + g)$ for instantaneous power control, $E_b/N_0 = 20$ dB, $G = 100$, a rectangular chip waveform, and various values of σ_e in decibels are illustrated in Figure 2. The block code is the binary Golay (23,12) code, for which $d = 7$ and $t = 3$. When the fading is slow and the interleaving is ineffective, the coding is, as expected, less effective than when the fading is fast and the interleaving is perfect, provided that σ_e remains the same. However, using the Cramer-Rao bound for the optimal estimate of the instantaneous power level, it is found [9] that σ_e^2 , expressed in decibels, is nearly proportional to the fading rate. Thus, even with optimal estimation for the power control and ideal interleaving, an increase in the fading rate by a factor of four doubles σ_e . If $\sigma_e \geq 1$ dB for slow fading, the figure indicates that fast fading at a rate four times that of the slow fading will increase P_{ib} . Allowing for suboptimal power estimation and imperfect interleaving, a doubling or tripling of the slow fading rate may well be sufficient to increase P_{ib} . The results for other block codes are similar. For slow or fast fading, the figure indicates the severe performance or reverse-link capacity loss when $\sigma_e > 2$ dB.

The use of spatial diversity or, in the presence of frequency-selective fading, a rake receiver will improve the performance of a direct-sequence CDMA system during both slow and fast fading, but the improvement is much greater when the fading is slow. As the fading rate increases, the accuracy of the estimation of the channel parameters used in the rake or diversity combiner becomes more difficult. When the channel-parameter estimation errors are too large to be accommodated, the coherent maximal-ratio combiner must be replaced by the suboptimal noncoherent equal-gain combiner, which does not require the estimation of channel parameters.

Suppose that instead of the instantaneous signal power, the local-mean power averaged over the fast fading is tracked, as has been assumed by many authors. If this tracking provides perfect power control of the local-mean power at the level S , then a received signal still exhibits fast fading relative to this level. If the fast fading has a Rayleigh distribution but the fading level is constant over a symbol interval, then the received energy per symbol is $E_s = E_{s0}\epsilon_0$, where ϵ_0 has the exponential probability density function given by

$$f_e(x) = \exp(-x)u(x) \quad (19)$$

where $u(x) = 1, x \geq 0$, and $u(x) = 0, x < 0$. Therefore, (4) implies that the conditional symbol error probability given E_t is

$$P_s(E_t) = \int_0^\infty \exp(-x)Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2x}{\gamma_0^{-1} + \sqrt{h}G^{-1}E_t/E_{s0}}}\right) dx = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \gamma_0^{-1} + \sqrt{h}G^{-1}E_t/E_{s0}\right)^{-1/2} \quad (20)$$

where $\gamma_0 = rE_b/N_0$. The total interference energy E_t is given by (9), where each ϵ_i is an independent, exponentially distributed random variable with mean equal to unity. Therefore, E_t has a gamma probability density function, and the symbol error probability is

Figure 2. Information-bit error rate for instantaneous power control, $E_b/N_0 = 20$ dB, $G = 100$, and the Golay (23,12) code with various values of σ_e in decibels.

$$P_s = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{K-2} \exp(-x)}{(K-2)! (1 + \gamma_0^{-1} + \sqrt{h} G^{-1} x)^{1/2}} dx, \quad (21)$$

perfect Impc

In Figure 3, the error rates for no coding, the Golay (23,12) code, and the binary BCH (63,30) code with $d = 13$ and $t = 6$ are shown, assuming that fast fading permits both perfect local-mean power control and perfect interleaving. A comparison of Figures 2 and 3 indicates that tracking of the local-mean power level is an inferior strategy for obtaining a large capacity compared with tracking of the instantaneous power level even if the latter tracking inaccuracy is substantial. Another problem with local-mean power control is that it requires time that may be unavailable for sporadic data.

Instantaneous power control specifies the power level in one diversity branch or for one rake component. Other branch signals or rake components exhibit fading relative to the specified power level. When local-mean power control is used, all branch signals or rake components fade relative to the local-mean power level. Thus, spatial or rake diversity will improve the system performance to roughly the same degree whatever the type of power control.

Apart from power control, instantaneous power measurements can be used to facilitate adaptive coding or adaptive transmitter diversity. Both of these techniques require timely information about the impact of the fading,

Figure 3. Information-bit error rate for local-mean power control, $E_b/N_0 = 20$ dB, and $G = 100$. Plots are for uncoded symbols, the Golay (23,12) code, and the BCH (63,30) code.

and this information is inherent in the instantaneous power measurements.

III. CONCLUSIONS

When fast fading causes large power-control errors, a direct-sequence CDMA network exhibits a significant performance degradation, notwithstanding the use of interleaving and channel coding. Adopting long-term-average instead of instantaneous power control will not cure the problem. To eliminate the problem by lowering the fading rate, one might reduce the Doppler spread by minimizing the carrier frequency of the direct-sequence signals. Another strategy is to limit the size of cells so that the network must cope with the more benign Ricean fading rather than Rayleigh fading, which is more likely to cause large power-control errors.

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